

Dichotomy of Newtonian Mechanics and a Wavelength in a Quantum Free Particle

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A classical Newtonian particle has momentum p , kinetic energy ($pp/2m_0$ nonrelativistically) and if p is constant, a constant velocity v . This constant velocity implies that for any dx , $dx=v dt$. In other words, there is infinite resolution. This viewpoint, however, is not completely correct, because a particle with momentum p is associated with a wavelength \hbar/p which manifests itself experimentally in a 2-slit experiment if the slits are about a wavelength apart. This experimental result suggests a discernment of space on the order of a wavelength or a probability distribution over \hbar/p which is nonuniform. This, however, seems to be completely at odds with the constant v picture, unless one considers $dx=v dt$ for dx greater than a wavelength.

In such a case, a function like $\cos(px)$ could describe the wavelength and 2-slit experiment. The wavelength, however, only exists if there is a p and if $\cos(px)$ is considered to be a probability, then $\cos(px)\cos(-px)$ would remove all information of p ($p=0$) implying that one should have the Newtonian picture, i.e smooth motion through all x points. This leads to $\exp(ipx)$, a two dimensional probability, which is consistent with both the wavelength and classical mechanics. We note that $\exp(ipx)$ is also needed to ensure conservation of momentum at each x point. As a result, there is a dichotomy incorporated in $\exp(ipx)$. If one examines $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ separately, then each has a momentum probability of $p\cos(px)$ and $p\sin(px)$ instead of p which only follows from $p \exp(ipx) = -i\hbar/dx \exp(ipx) / (\exp(ipx))$. In other words, it is not only v which is an average, but it seems that p is also an average and there each component of $\exp(ipx)$ represents momentum fluctuations, but in a systematic manner. This is why $\exp(ipx) + \exp(-ipx)$ yields $2 \cos(px)$, but its average momentum proportional to $|p| \sin(px) / \cos(px)$. This fluctuating essence is still present in the free particle $\exp(ipx)$, but is masked by the two components.

As a result, a quantum description of a free particle describes both a wavelength and classical motion. If one were to ask: How does one transform from $\exp(ipx)$ to Newtonian mechanics, one might argue that one can simply drop $\exp(ipx)$ and use $p=\text{constant}$, $v =\text{constant}$ which is in fact what Newtonian mechanics yields. The issue is then dealing with a bound system. Quantum mechanics is associated with describing spatial resolutions, even in the bound state problem where there are crests and troughs, albeit of different heights and lengths. In such a case, one has: $a(p)\exp(ipx) + a(-p)\exp(-ipx)$ etc. If $a(p)=a(-p)$ then one has $\cos(px)$ instead of $\exp(ipx)$ which is fine because physically the wavelength region exists and is delineated by probability and here one has an OR situation and does not need two dimensions for an AND situation.

The point we wish to suggest is that the Schrodinger equation really creates the resolution pattern of the quantum system such that it is compatible with the classical equation: $KE_{ave}(x) + V(x) = E_n$. We thus argue that there is no reason that a high energy limit treatment of quantum mechanics should collapse to classical mechanics. $KE_{ave}(x)+V(x)=E_n$ is classical mechanics for all energy levels and as the energy level becomes high, the resolution becomes tiny, but still exists, because there could still be a theoretically a 2-slit apparatus which could interact with the particle.

Fitting Quantum Mechanics to the 2-Slit Experiment

One may consider carrying out 2-slit experiments for various constant p values such that one finds that when the slits are about \hbar/p apart, an interference pattern occurs. Thus, experimentally, one may associate a particle with constant p with a length \hbar/p . This, however, seems to completely contradict Newtonian mechanics which suggests that a constant p particle moves smoothly through space time with constant v . A length \hbar/p must be physically discerned by the particle suggesting a nonuniform probability distribution over an x base \hbar/p long.

One cannot, however, disregard the Newtonian idea of constant v and a quick fix seems to involve assuming $dx=vdt$ as long as $dx>\hbar/p$. Another problem, however, arises. If one considers a probability distribution which is nonuniform over \hbar/p to discern a wavelength, then p and $-p$ have the same wavelength, but:

$$P_1(p)P_1(-p) = P(-p+ -p) = P(0) \text{ which cannot have any wavelength ((1))}$$

Thus, one expects a power law c power (p), but this must also exist in x . As argued in other notes, we use $\exp(ipx)$. In other words, $\cos(px)$ is good enough to describe 2-slit interference, but it cannot show that for p and $-p$ that momentum and hence a wavelength disappears. It also cannot show conservation of momentum if one defines it through:

$$\exp(-i p_{\text{final}} x) \exp(i p_{\text{initial}} x) = 1 \text{ if } p_{\text{final}} = p_{\text{initial}} ((2))$$

If one were to only use $\cos(px)$ then $\cos(-p_{\text{final}} x) \cos(p_{\text{initial}} x) = \cos(-px)\cos(px)$.

As a result, the two dimensionality of $\exp(ipx)$ serves to both show the wavelength linked with a probability, built-in conservation of momentum and consistency with Newtonian mechanics.

If one were to ask: How does one extract Newtonian mechanics from $\exp(ipx)$, one might simply argue that one uses $p=\text{constant}$, v constant and ignores \hbar/p . In other words, there is no mathematical limiting process needed.

Momentum Fluctuations

We noted that $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ by themselves define a length \hbar/p , but seem to be at odds with v constant and infinite x resolution. A way to avoid this issue is to use the two dimensional $\exp(ipx)$ such that $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx) = 1$. Nevertheless, \hbar/p is still contained in both $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ and is physical. The two dimensional feature is then somewhat of a "fix" to create the sense of Newtonian space when in fact there is wavelength discretization. The nonuniform probability distributions $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ suggest that one has constant p only on average, although this average exists at each x point. In particular:

$$-i\hbar/dx \cos(px) = p \sin(px) \text{ which has a range of values as does } -i\hbar/dx \sin(px) ((3))$$

It is only when one uses: $-i\hbar d/dx \exp(ipx) / \exp(ipx)$ that one obtains p .

In other words, momentum fluctuations which are systematic convert $\cos(px)$ to $\sin(px)$ and vice versa so that there is the sense of constant p at each x , when in fact momentum fluctuations are present.

These ideas may seem a little vague for a free particle, but are manifested more clearly for a bound particle.

Bound Particle.

We first consider a p OR $-p$ situation. In such a case, one does not need to worry about p AND $-p$ removing momentum and hence the wavelength \hbar/p . P or $-p$ means that there is clearly a wavelength of \hbar/p . The fact that $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ interfere means that one cannot determine whether the particle has p or $-p$. This is not the same scenario as classical statistical mechanics in which some particles have p and other $-p$. Here there is a single particle and there is no way of knowing whether it has p or $-p$ at any x . This suggests a fluctuation in p , we argue. Furthermore, there is no sense of smooth motion in one direction and so no need of a complex probability sum. Given that p and $-p$ are both compatible with \hbar/p (wavelength), this feature should be present. Thus:

$$\exp(ipx) + \exp(-ipx) = 2\cos(px) \quad ((4))$$

$\cos(px)$ is physical because it shows the \hbar/p wavelength. Moreover, it shows the associated momentum fluctuation through:

$$(2) -d/dx \cos(px) / \cos(px) = -2 p \sin(px) / \cos(px) \quad ((5))$$

This holds even though p appears in ((5)). This we argue is the physics associated with creating the crest-trough pattern which is verifiable through experiment.

One main issue we wish to discuss is the nondiscernment of p and $-p$, i.e. the interference of $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ versus a classical particle moving forward and backwards as in a Newtonian problem of a particle bouncing back and forth. We argue that these are different in the sense that the calculation of $\cos(px)$ serves to show the wavelength. This wavelength, however, depends on p which is consistent with a Newtonian concept of p and constant v . Thus, even though the quantum calculation yields $\cos(px)$ and there is fluctuation of momentum, there should also be a rms view of a particle moving forwards and backwards with p .

This follows from:

$$p^2/2m (\exp(ipx)+\exp(-ipx)) / (\exp(ipx) +\exp(-ipx)) = p^2/2m \text{ or } p_{rms} = p \text{ or } -p \quad ((6))$$

Thus, quantum mechanics yields both the Newtonian rms picture in which there is discernment of motion, i.e. p and $-p$ in ((6)) are distinguishable in ((6)), but not in ((5)) whose purpose is to find the wavelength. As a result, one again does not have any kind of limiting situation (i.e. high

energy case) which converts the quantum picture to the classical. As a specific example, consider an infinite well potential for which p above becomes p_{average} .

As a second situation, consider an arbitrary $V(x)$. In such a case, a quantum calculation should compute the spatial resolution pattern which is necessarily associated with momentum fluctuations in a systematic manner. Quantum calculations use $a(p)\exp(ipx) + a(-p)\exp(-ipx)$ (for $a(p)=a(-p)$ or $a(p)=-a(-p)$). This means that p and $-p$ cannot be distinguished which is completely unclassical, but this is fine because the calculation is to determine the crests and troughs. The calculation, however, cannot be fully removed from classical physics at any energy level because there is still the notion of classical conservation of energy at each x point demonstrated by the use of $V(x)$. Thus, if one uses $a(p)\sqrt{p/2m} \exp(ipx) + a(-p)\sqrt{p/2m} \exp(-ipx)$, then $p/2m$ is the same for p and $-p$ whether they are discerned or not and one may calculate an average kinetic energy. From this one may find p_{rms} which represents classical motion to the right or to the left in fixed intervals, even though $\exp(ipx) + \exp(-ipx)$ does not discern between p and $-p$. In other words, one may still have a crest-trough picture and momentum fluctuations while still insisting on average energy conservation at each x point, which is a classical idea for any energy level.. Thus:

$$-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W/W + V(x) = E_n \quad ((7))$$

As a result, we argue that both classical mechanics and quantum mechanics are present at each energy level. Quantum mechanics is present because one has crests-troughs and momentum fluctuations: $p_{\text{ave}} = -i dW/dx / W$, while classical mechanics is present because: $KE_{\text{ave}}(x) + V(x) = E_n$. One must be careful, however, with the energy conservation equation, because spatial resolution is of the order of the base of a crest or trough. One cannot discern within, so one would be hard-pressed to argue for classical motion at low energy levels. When the crests and troughs become very narrow, then one may discern x points closely.

In such a case how does one obtain classical physics? We still argue that there is no mathematical limiting process for high energy levels. When quantum resolution becomes very tiny, one may argue that p_{rms} (which always holds) is not really limited by resolution and so one may simply use $p_{\text{rms}}(x)$ and ignore the crests-troughs. The crests-troughs, however, are still physical in the sense that one may still have a 2-slit experiment which could discern them

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that experimentally 2-slit interference for a particle with constant p implies the discernment of a length \hbar/p by the particle. This, in turn, suggests a nonuniform probability distribution over x which is at odds with the particle spending the same amount of time in each dx as suggested by Newtonian mechanics. A work-around is to suggest that dx cannot be smaller than \hbar/p . A second problem however, arises if one suggests that not only does one have a nonuniform probability $P_1(p,x)$, but that $P_1(p,x)P_1(-p,x) = P_1(0,x)$ suggesting no wavelength because there is no p . In other words, p information and the wavelength disappear in such a picture. This suggests a two dimensional probability $\exp(ipx)$ with each component $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ demonstrating \hbar/p , but the complex combination allows for the

Newtonian viewpoint. Nevertheless, there seems to be momentum fluctuation in a systematic manner linked with $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ such that $-i\hbar d/dx \exp(ipx)/\exp(ipx) = p$. Thus, we suggest that not only does $\exp(ipx)$ give the Newtonian sense of smooth motion in any dx , but that it is also linked with a constant p when in fact there are momentum fluctuations even for a free particle. Thus, we suggest that to obtain Newtonian mechanics from $\exp(ipx)$, one needs to drop $\exp(ipx)$ and simply use $p = \text{constant}$, $v = \text{constant}$.

We then turn to the case of a bound state for which one uses $a(p)\exp(ipx) + a(-p)\exp(-ipx)$ terms with $a(p) = a(-p)$ or $a(p) = -a(-p)$. We suggest that interference means that one cannot discern p or $-p$ at any x . This then leads to $2\cos(px)$ which is not compatible with smooth motion in x (which is fine if one cannot discern p or $-p$), but still shows \hbar/p . This, then is not a classical picture of p for some time and $-p$ for another. To obtain that scenario, one uses: $\frac{p^2}{2m} \frac{a(p)\exp(ipx) + p^2/2m a(-p)\exp(-ipx)}{a(p)\exp(ipx) + a(-p)\exp(ipx)}$. This leads to $p^2/2m$ so that $-p$ and p are discernible. Thus, two processes are in play. For a bound state, one uses Newtonian conservation of energy at each x point, i.e. $-1/2m d/dx dW/dx/W + V(x) = E_n$ where $W(x) = \sum \text{over } p a(p)\exp(ipx)$. The fact that $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ interfere means that one cannot discern between p and $-p$, but an energy equation is fine because both have $p^2/2m$. Thus, $prms$ from $KE_{ave}(x)$ can be considered to move in one direction for some time and then in another. The crests-troughs which emerge, however, tell what spatial resolution one has and if they are large (base), then there is little resolution. In other words, the quantum calculation's goal is to find the crests-troughs (which are associated with momentum fluctuations: $-i\hbar dW/dx/W$) and use interference which is unclassical. Nevertheless, an average classical energy $KE_{ave}(x)$ is imposed so that $prms(x)$ represents the classical velocity at any energy level (although it cannot be resolved at low energies). At high energies the crests-troughs become very narrow and the classical approach is to ignore them and only use $prms(x)$. A 2-slit experiment could discern them..